

EFFECT OF POWER YOGA WITH IRON SUPPLEMENTATION ON HEMATOLOGICAL VARIABLES AMONG INTERCOLLEGIATE VOLLEY BALL PLAYERS

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Abstract:

There are many different forms of yoga and Power yoga is one of them. Power yoga is a term coined in the West and it describes a vigorous fitness based approach to the Vinayasa style of yoga. The word "power" in the phrase describes the intensity this kind of yoga involves. Most of the exercises in Power yoga are modeled on the Ashtanga style of yoga. Both these kinds of yoga (Power and Ashtanga) use the Vinayasa poses. Vinayasa poses link together the principal poses in a yoga class. Unlike other forms of yoga. Iron is a trace mineral which plays important role to make hemoglobin. The role of hemoglobin is transport of oxygen from the lungs to exercising muscle. It plays important role in endurance sports. The purpose of this study was to find out the influence of iron supplementation and Power Yoga should improve the Inter Collegiate Badminton players. To achieve the purpose of this study, forty five male inter collegiate badminton players selected from MGR University, Chennai. The subjects divided into three equal groups. The test Hemoglobin, Red blood cells conducted before and after eight weeks of Power Yoga with iron supplementation. After the pre test the Experimental group I underwent Power Yoga with iron supplementation and Experimental group II underwent Power Yoga without iron supplementation and Control group underwent only pre and post test without Power Yoga with iron supplementation. The pre and post test results were analyzed by using "Analysis of covariance" (ANCOVA). The results of this study proved that there was significant improvement in Inter Collegiate Badminton players after eight weeks of Power Yoga with iron supplementation.

Key Words: Power Yoga, Red Blood Cells, Hemoglobin, Iron Supplementation.

Introduction:

Power yoga moves and exercises have been invented to strengthen the whole body and develop on a person's willpower. These workout are known to burn calories, improve the muscle mass, reduce fat and increase the Basal Metabolic Rate. People often do power yoga for weight loss. It is generally recommended to do power yoga workout about thrice a week and for 45 minutes each time. Before you start doing power yoga postures to burn calories, you may want to speak with a medical practitioner.

Power yoga is an impressive form of practice with very stimulating styles. This is of course, the American way of doing Ashtanga yoga or their interpretation of it. The core of Power yoga is about a vigorous workout that builds muscles and gets people to sweat. This form of yoga is not for calm, mild or moderate yoga students, and for those who love a fast-paced workout. It is also advised to learn this form of yoga from a qualified Power yoga teacher and not attempt it on their own.

Iron functions as the most important role by carrying oxygen components in the blood. It is an essential mineral and a part of hemoglobin. Deficiency of iron may lead to tiredness and other physical disorders because of the deficiency of oxygen. Badminton players are often at great risk to have iron insufficiency. Iron performs the activity to store oxygen in the muscle cells and also increase energy to the body. The deficiency of iron in the body fails to produce adenosine triphosphate (ATP), an important element that runs the body to function in a proper way. So, it is quite obvious that a person having iron deficiency always seen to suffer from fatigue and weariness even when their hemoglobin levels are at normal level. Iron deficiency is the most common single nutrient deficiency disease in the world and is a major concern for 15% of the world population. Several studies reported that endurance athletes, who are involved in heavy training, may be prone to iron deficiency. Nutrition not only plays a role in performance, but it also helps to prevent injuries, enhance recovery from exercise.

Role of Red Blood Cells in Training:

Red blood cells have several important roles to play in our bodies. The primary function of red blood cells is to carry oxygen from the lungs to the tissues around body. As a secondary function, they are also a key

player in getting waste carbon dioxide from tissues to lungs, where it can be breathed out. Ability of red blood cells to carry carbon dioxide is a waste product of metabolism in every cell of body. The process by which red blood cells transport carbon dioxide is different than oxygen transport. RBC contains an enzyme called carbonic anhydrase. As the carbon dioxide enters the RBC, this enzyme with the help of water converts it into chemical called bicarbonate. Bicarbonate is used to control the pH in blood and it later excreted through lungs or kidney.

Role of Hemoglobin in Training:

Hemoglobin is a protein found in red blood cells, carries most of the oxygen in the blood. Hemoglobin can bind oxygen or carbon dioxide; the amount of oxygen bound to hemoglobin is determined by the oxygen concentration, carbon dioxide concentration and pH. During exercise the metabolic activity is high, more acids (hydrogen ions, lactic acid) are produced and the local pH is lower than normal. The low pH reduces the attraction between oxygen and hemoglobin and causes the hemoglobin to release more oxygen than usual. This increases the oxygen delivered to the muscle.

Statement of the Problem:

The purpose of this study was to find out the effect of Power Yoga with iron supplementation should improve the Inter Collegiate volley ball players.

Methodology:

To achieve the purpose of this study forty five Inter Collegiate volley ball players were randomly selected from Karikal, The subject's age group ranged between 21-23 years. They were divided into three equal groups.

Selection of the Variables:

- Independent variables - Power Yoga with iron supplementation.
- Dependent variables - hemoglobin and red blood cells.

Experimental Design:

The study was formulated as a true random group design, consisting of a pre test and post test. To achieve the purpose of the study forty five Inter Collegiate volley ball players were randomly selected and assigned to three equal groups. The groups were assigned as Experimental group I, II and Control group. Experimental group I underwent Power Yoga with iron supplementation. Experimental group II underwent Power Yoga without iron supplementation. Control group underwent only pre and post test without Power Yoga with iron supplementation. Pre and post test of hemoglobin and Red blood cells was conducted for the subjects before and after eight weeks of Power Yoga with iron supplementation.

Iron Supplementation:

Iron supplementation had taken by the Experimental group I through natural iron supplementation such as Green leaf, joggery with dates with and after the breakfast and lunch for the period of eight weeks.

Collection of Data:

Blood sample collected from the subjects to check the hematological variable such as hemoglobin and red blood cells before and after eight weeks of Power Yoga with iron supplementation. The blood sample was analyzed in the standard biochemistry lab.

Statistical Technique:

Analysis of Covariance statistical technique was used, to test the significant difference among the treatment groups. Scheffe's post hoc test was used to determine the paired mean significant difference. Thirumalaisamy R. (1988).

Results and Discussion:

Table 1: Computation of Analysis of Covariance of Hemoglobin

(Scores in gm%)

Mean	Exp I	Exp II	Control	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	Obtained F Values
Pre Test Mean	12.76	12.76	12.77	Between	0.00	2	0.00	0.00
				Within	39.52	42	0.94	
Post Test Mean	13.1	13.69	12.81	Between	6.12	2	3.06	4.44*
				Within	28.96	42	0.69	
Adjusted Mean	13.10	13.70	12.80	Between	6.19	2	3.09	5.36*
				Within	23.669	41	0.58	

Table F ratio at 0.05 level of confidence for 2 and 42 (df) = 3.23

Result of the Variable:

From these analyses of data Experimental group I which was Iron supplementation and Power Yoga group increased the level of hemoglobin in the blood compared with other two groups. The increased level of hemoglobin due to iron supplementation it helps to boost the production of hemoglobin in the blood.

Table 2: Computation of Analysis of Covariance of Red Blood Cells

(Scores in million cells per cubic millimeter)

Mean	Exp I	Exp II	Control	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	Obtained F Values
Pre Test Mean	4.26	4.26	4.26	Between	0.00	2	0.00	0.01
				Within	1.25	42	0.03	
Post Test Mean	4.36	4.30	4.26	Between	0.69	2	0.35	13.42*
				Within	1.09	42	0.03	
Adjusted Mean	4.37	4.26	4.26	Between	0.69	2	0.35	14.53*
				Within	0.98	41	0.02	

Table F ratio at 0.05 level of confidence for 2 and 42 (df) = 3.23

Result of the Variable:

The increased level of hemoglobin and red blood cells helps to transport of oxygen to the exercising muscle and helps to promote the production of ATP. The adequate supply of oxygen to the exercising muscle helps to reduce accumulation of lactic acid and maintain pH level through which reduces fatigue. This helps to boost the performance of the badminton players. From these analyses of results eight weeks of Power Yoga with Iron supplementation improved the performance of inter collegiate badminton players.

Conclusion:

Within the limitations and delimitations of the study, the following conclusions were drawn,

- There was a significant improvement in hematological among Inter Collegiate volley ball players due to influence of Power Yoga with iron supplementation.
- Experimental group I had significantly increased in the red blood cells and hemoglobin Hemtological variables than the experimental group II and control group.
- From these statistical analyses of results of the study concluded that eight weeks of Power Yoga with Iron supplementation improved the Inter Collegiate Men Badminton players.

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